

A Novel Green Catalytic Synthesis of Chalcone Derivatives by Aldol Condensation Reaction

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ABSTRACT:

Aldol condensations are important in organic synthesis, providing a good way to form carbon-carbon bonds. The "aldol" (aldehyde + alcohol) product is a structural unit found in many naturally occurring molecules and pharmaceuticals, and is therefore important. In an Aldol condensation an enolate ion reacts with a carbonyl compound to form a β -hydroxyaldehyde or β -hydroxyketone, followed by dehydration to give a conjugated enone. The reaction involves the nucleophilic addition of an enolate to an aldehyde to form a β -hydroxy carbonyl. The β -hydroxy carbonyl is readily dehydrated under mild conditions. The aldol reaction occurs under both acidic and basic conditions. The reaction we will be doing this research involves the reaction between benzaldehyde and acetone to do a double Aldol Condensation.

INTRODUCTION:**Synthesis and evaluation of chalcone derivatives by Crossed Aldol condensation:**

One of the goals of green chemistry is the use of less hazardous solvents. The synthesis of chalcones can even be done with no solvent. However, the use of water as a solvent leads to a more uniform product.

A set of chalcones will be synthesized in this thesis, using a variety of *para*-substituted benzaldehydes and acetophenones. After purification by recrystallization and characterization by melting point, infrared and NMR spectroscopy, the chalcones will be readily identifiable.

Chalcone is a class of open-chain flavonoids that is not only biosynthesized by plants but also can be prepared synthetically. Chalcone is an aromatic ketone that forms the central core for a variety of important biological compounds. Other names for chalcone are benzalacetophenone and phenyl styryl ketone.

Chalcones show antibacterial, antifungal, antitumor and anti-inflammatory properties. They are also intermediates in the biosynthesis of flavonoids, which are substances widespread in plants and with an array of biological activities. Chalcones are also intermediates in the Auwers synthesis of flavones. Chalcone can be prepared by an aldol condensation between a benzaldehyde and an acetophenone in the presence of a catalyst. Aldol condensation is also known as Claisen- Schmidt reaction.

The aldol condensation relies on the reactivity of a carbonyl group to build a new carbon-carbon bond. The aldol reaction is one of the most powerful methods available for forming a carbon-carbon bond. In this reaction, the conjugate base of an aldehyde or ketone adds to the carbonyl group of another aldehyde or ketone to give a β -hydroxyaldehyde or β -hydroxyketone product. This is the intermediate product of the crossed aldol reaction.

Chalcones are popular intermediates for synthesizing various heterocyclic compounds. Chalcones represent a group of compounds with interesting biological activities that are formed from a Claisen-Schmidt reaction between a benzaldehyde and an acetophenone in the presence of NaOH as a catalyst. In this study six different chalcones were synthesized.

In this synthesis five chalcones was carried out by shaking the benzaldehyde (4-nitro, 4-hydroxy, 4-chloro, 4-methoxy, 4-methyl) and acetophenone in the presence of potassium hydroxide and PEG-400 as a solvent in iodine flask. Chalcones were obtained in high yields (80-92%) and high purity. The results seemed to indicate the success of the synthesis which is simple, highly efficient and eco-friendly.

The prevalence of diabetes mellitus is on the increase and needs to be addressed appropriately and significant advances have been made in the past few years in the isolation and preparation of several chalcone derivatives.

Figure 1 : Chalcone

EXPERIMENTAL WORK:**Preliminary optimization experiments**

Preliminary screening of the reaction conditions by using benzaldehyde (0.5 mmol) and acetophenone (1.0 mmol) as a model reaction showed that PEG-400 afforded the corresponding Chalcone product in good yields within 1 h at physiological temperature at room temperature.

As indicated in Table 1, the best ratio of PEG-400 to starting material is 100 μ L, but as the yields were poor, we decided to investigate the effect of different solvents and time duration increased on the reaction in an effort to increase the observed yields. To reach this goal, we tested different solvents for the same aldol condensation reaction in the presence of 100 μ L PEG-400 as catalyst for 30 minutes. Our results showed that 100 μ L PEG-400 as catalyst is the best concentration (Table 1, entry 4). These results are comparable with other catalytic solvent in table 2.

Finally, to study the effect of catalyst we explored some reaction conditions for aldol condensation of acetophenone and benzaldehyde in the presence of 100 μ L PEG 400 as catalyst.

Table 1 Optimization of amount of PEG-400 in the aldol condensation of Acetophenone and benzaldehyde at room temperature.

Entry	Amount of PEG-400 in μL	Time in Minutes	Yield%
1	25	10	No reaction
2	50	10	30
3	75	10	45
4	100	10	55
5	125	10	40

Table 2 Optimization of aldol condensation of Acetophenone and benzaldehyde with or without PEG as catalyst at room temperature.

Entry	Solvent	Time in Minutes	Yield%
1	PEG-400	30-40	90
2	EtOH	30-40	Trace
3	MeOH	30-40	Trace
4	Ether	30-40	No Reaction
5	Toluene	30-40	No Reaction
6	THF	30-40	No reaction
7	Acetonitrile	30-40	Trace

SCIENTIFIC NOVELTY:**Materials****TABLE 3 : List of materials used in the study**

S. No.	Excipient	Grade	Manufacturer
1	Acetophenone	A.R.	S. D. Fine Pvt. Ltd.
2	Benzaldehyde	A.R.	S. D. Fine Pvt. Ltd.
3	4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	A.R.	S. D. Fine Pvt. Ltd.
4	4-Methylbenzaldehyde	A.R.	S. D. Fine Pvt. Ltd.
5	4-Methoxybenzaldehyde	A.R.	S. D. Fine Pvt. Ltd.
6	4-Nitrobenzaldehyde	A.R.	S. D. Fine Pvt. Ltd.
7	4-Cholorobenzaldehyde	A.R.	S. D. Fine Pvt. Ltd.
8	PEG-400	A.R.	Qualigens
9	Potassium hydroxide	A.R.	Qualigens
10	Hexane	A.R.	Qualigens
11.	Ethyl Acetate	A.R.	Qualigens
12.	Ethanol	A.R.	Qualigens

General Procedure:**Sample Preparation:**

1. Place 0.5 moles of benzaldehyde, 1.0 mole of acetophenone, and 100 μ L of PEG-400 (as a solvent) in a conical test tube. Mix until completely dissolved.
2. Add 14mg potassium hydroxide solution. Mix the contents until precipitation is observed.
3. Let the mixture stand for another 20 minutes with occasional shaking.
4. After the 20-minute period is completed, cool the mixture in an ice bath for 10 minutes.
5. Place the conical test tube in the centrifuge (remember to cork and counterbalance). Centrifuge for a few minutes. Decant to remove the liquid from the tube. If it is difficult to separate, use a cotton-plugged Pasteur Pipette. (In order to assure that no solid product is transferred out of the test tube, I could take a very small piece of cotton, and plug up the tip of the pipette from the outside, such that only liquids are transferred into the pipette, leaving the solids behind in the conical test tube.)
6. Wash the crystals with 2 mL ice-cold distill water. Centrifuge and decant. Wash with the second portion of 2 mL ice-cold distill water. Centrifuge and decant.
7. Recrystallize the solid product in the same conical test tube, using 95% ethanol as the solvent. Place the test tube in a water bath on the hot plate. Preheat the ethanol in the water bath then add *drop wise* into the test tube until all the crystals dissolve. Heating (keep temperature lower than the boiling

point of the ethanol), stirring, and adding more ethanol will help with the dissolving. Let the solution cool slowly and without agitation. Once crystals are formed, place the test tube in the ice bath to maximize the amount of the crystals.

8. Collect the product via vacuum filtration (rinse with ice-cold ethanol) and allow it to dry. Note that it may need to tear the filter paper if we have very little product.

9. Weigh the product. Measure the melting point, TLC (for yield percentage) and the IR, NMR spectrum of our obtained product.

The functional group of the products was identified by using Fourier transform infra-red (FTIR), whereas amount, type and proton position were analyzed by using H-NMR 500 MHz.

Synthesis of chalcone

The synthesis of chalcone was carried out *via* Crossed Aldol or Claisen-Schmidt condensation of commercially available Acetophenone (1.0 mmol or 117 μ L, bp 202 $^{\circ}$ C, density 1.03 g/mL) and Benzaldehyde (0.5 mmol or 55 μ L, bp 178-179 $^{\circ}$ C, density 1.04 g/mL) in the presence of KOH (14mg.) as a base in PEG-400(100 μ L). The reaction was initiated by removal of a proton from the α -carbon of Acetophenone to form a resonance-stabilized enolate ion by the base. This was followed by the nucleophilic enolate attacks on the electrophilic carbonyl carbon of benzaldehyde resulting in a new carbon carbon bond formation. This reaction joined the α -carbon of acetophenone to the carbonyl carbon of benzaldehyde to form intermediate. The final step of this reaction was protonation and deprotonation by hydroxide ion to form an α,β -unsaturated ketone, chalcone or 1,3-diphenylpropenone as a light yellow solid in 78.33% yield. The reaction mechanism for chalcone synthesis is illustrated in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1: Chalcone synthesis reaction using benzaldehyde and acetophenone in presence of green catalyst PEG-400.

Table 4: Preparation of Chalcone and their derivatives by Cross Aldol condensation reaction with PEG-400 by changing the R-group in Benzaldehyde

Entry	R ₂	R ₁	Yield (%)
1	H	H	78
2	H	4-CH ₃	82
3	H	4-Cl	85
4	H	4-OH	80
5	H	4-NO ₂	90
6	H	4-OCH ₃	92

Synthesis of designed molecules 3-(4-methylphenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (Compound 1)

A solution Acetophenone (117.0 μ L, 1.0 mmol) stirred in ethanol (8ml) was added with 4-Methylbenzaldehyde (60 μ L, 0.5mmol) in a conical test tube (25 mL) and then KOH (14 mg) was added into PEG-400(100 μ L) drop wise into it.

The mixture was stirred in ice coldwater bath until it solidified. Then solidified mass is kept in cold condition overnight and after that solidified mass separated and dried on room temperature to give compound.

Synthesis of designed molecules 3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (Compound 2)

A solution Acetophenone (117.0 μL , 1.0 mmol) stirred in ethanol (8 ml) was added with 4-Chlorobenzaldehyde (70 μL , 0.5mmol) in a conical test tube and then KOH (14 mg) was added into PEG-400(100 μL) drop wise into it. The mixture was stirred in ice coldwater bath until it solidified. Then solidified mass is kept in cold condition overnight and after that solidified mass separated and dried on room temperature to give compound.

Synthesis of designed molecules 3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (Compound 3)

A solution Acetophenone (117.0 μL , 1.0 mmol) stirred in ethanol (8 ml) was added with 4- Hydroxybenzaldehyde (61 μL , 0.5mmole) in a conical test tube and then KOH (14 mg) was added into PEG-400(100 μL) drop wise into it. The

mixture was stirred in ice coldwater bath until it solidified. Then solidified mass is kept in cold condition overnight and after that solidified mass separated and dried on room temperature to give compound.

Synthesis of designed molecules 3-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (Compound 4)

A solution Acetophenone (117.0 μL , 1.0 mmol) stirred in ethanol (8 ml) was added with 4-nitrobenzaldehyde (75.5 μL , 0.5mmole) in a conical test tube and then KOH (14 mg) was added into PEG-400(100 μL) drop wise into it. The mixture was stirred in ice coldwater bath until it solidified. Then solidified mass is kept in cold condition overnight and after that solidified mass separated and dried on room temperature to give compound.

Synthesis of designed molecules 3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (Compound 5)

A solution Acetophenone (117.0 μL , 1.0 mmol) stirred in ethanol (8 ml) was added with 4-Methoxybenzaldehyde or *p*-anisaldehyde (37.5 μL , 0.5mmole) in a conical test tube and then KOH (14 mg) was added into PEG-400(100 μL) drop wise into it. The mixture was stirred in ice coldwater bath until it solidified.

Then solidified mass is kept in cold condition overnight and after that solidified mass separated and dried on room temperature to give compound.

Analytical thin-layer chromatography (TLC):

Analytical thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was carried out on precoated plates SiO₂ (silica gel 60, F 254, Merck). The spots were viewed under ultraviolet (UV) light. The progress of the reaction was monitored on TLC plate using hexane: ethyl acetate (8:2). After completion, the mixture was poured into water and was extracted with EtOAc. The solvent was removed and crude product was subjected to column chromatography to obtained pure Chalcone. The PEG was recovered from the aqueous layer. About 5-10 mg of the Chalcone was dissolved 100 mL ethanol solvent, where it was soluble. A baseline at the base of TLC plate by a pencil marker at a minimum of 0.5-1 cm from the bottom end. A spot on 2 to 3 times the base line using capillary by dipping the capillary in the Chalcone solution mixture. The Eluent solution (Mobile Phase) prepared with Pure cyclohexane, 8:2 ethyl acetate ratio by volume.

To a beaker, 0.02 to 0.08 cm of solvent was placed in bottom. The TLC plate was spotted with Chalcone sample, then TLC was placed in the beaker covered with glass lead. The eluent solvent was allowed to rise up to the 1 cm or just below pencil mark end of TLC plate.

The percentage yield was measured by chromatographic method using a thin layer chromatography-densitometry scanner based on the formula:

$$\text{Yield} = \frac{\text{Product concentration} \times \text{concentration (TLC scanner)}}{\text{Theoretic weight}} \times 100\%$$

Crystallization of the desired product was achieved by hexane and ethyl acetate into ice. The solution was then filtered through 41 whatman filter paper and solid product i.e. Chalcone was kept for characterization by FT-IR spectroscopy.

Synthesis of designed molecules (Compound 1)

The representative NMR spectra for the starting material & the product were characterized below.

Synthesis of designed molecules (Compound 2)

The representative NMR spectra for the starting material & the product were characterized below.

Synthesis of designed molecules (Compound 3)

The representative NMR spectra for the starting material & the product were characterized below.

Synthesis of designed molecules (Compound 4)

The representative NMR spectra for the starting material & the product were characterized below.

Synthesis of designed molecules (Compound 5)

The representative NMR spectra for the starting material & the product were characterized below.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR):

The scanning electron microscopy is a type of electron microscopy that images the sample surface by scanning it with a high-energy beam of electrons. The

electrons interact with the atoms that make up the sample producing signals that contain information about the sample's surface topography, composition and other properties such as electrical conductivity.

NMR was used to investigate surfactant state physical structure of the prepared chalcone. NMR photographs of chalcone and its surfactant medium were obtained using a scanning electron microscope model. The ^1H (500 MHz) and ^{13}C -NMR (500 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker advance NEO NMR spectrometer (with tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal reference for ^1H and ^{13}C using CDCl_3 and DMSO-d_6 as solvent).

Figure 2 : NMR of compound 4 or 3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one synthesized by general procedure

Figure 3 : NMR of 4-Methoxybenzaldehyde or *p*-anisaldehyde for compound 5 synthesized by general procedure

¹H NMR spectrum of compound is showing signals for both aliphatic and aromatic protons. ¹H NMR spectrum showed a pair of doublets corresponding the range of 7.82 to 7.68 ppm and 8.0 to 8.33 ppm respectively.

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 8.24-8.30 (e, 2H, 5H, 3H), 8.0- 8.05 (e, 2H, 2H, 6H), 7.78-7.82 (a, 2H, 6'H, 2'H), 7.6-7.68 (b, 2H,5'H, 2'H), 7.5-7.56 (c, 3H, 3'H, 4'H, 5'H).

RESULTS:

The ¹H NMR spectrum for the starting material, *p*-anisaldehyde, is shown in Figure 2. Here, the resonances for the aldehyde and oxymethyl proton environments can be easily identified.

The two remaining resonances, belonging to the 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring, can be assigned based on inductive effects of the substituents, *i.e.* the aldehyde carbonyl group pulls electron density away from the aromatic ring, deshielding the *ortho* protons and shields those in the *meta* position. The oxymethyl group has the opposite effect.

Figure 3 shows the ^1H NMR spectrum of recrystallized 4-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-3-buten-2-one. The diagnostic methyl resonances at 2.35 ppm and 3.83 ppm are the terminal methyl at position 1 and oxymethyl on the aromatic ring, respectively. The remaining resonances between 6.37–7.69 ppm should account for the remaining six protons in four chemical environments – *i.e.* the two alkene protons and the two sets of aromatic protons.

The overlap of these resonances complicates the assignment of their chemical shifts and multiplicities. By turning to the 2D J -resolved and COSY experiments in Figures 2 and 3, this region can be observed in more detail. In the 2D J -resolved experiment, J -coupling constants are mapped against the proton chemical shift. This allows the chemical shifts of proton resonances to be accurately measured by examining the f2 dimension, while their coupling constants can be measured in the f1 dimension.

Thus, in Figure 3, two doublets with 16.4 Hz coupling constants can be identified at 6.56 and 7.51 ppm, and two doublets of 8.5 Hz at 6.89 and 7.50 ppm. The magnitude of the coupling constants obtained here also point to the location of each spin system – 16.4 Hz is typical for a 1, 2-disubstituted alkene with an *E* geometry, while 8.5 Hz is consistent with protons on an aromatic ring in an *ortho* arrangement.

The COSY experiment is used to identify spin-coupling partners, usually over 2–4 bonds. In the COSY of Product A (Figure 3), the same proton pairs identified in the 2D J -resolved experiment are shown to correlate to each other through interpretation of cross-peaks read from the diagonal of the 2D spectrum. Thus, the resonances at 6.89 ppm and 7.50 ppm (green box) form one spin system, while the resonances at 6.56 ppm and 7.52 ppm (blue box) form the other spin system.

These correlations further validate the proximity of these resonances to each other. Assignment of these proton resonances to their actual positions in the molecule can be made based on the inductive effects of the nearby functional groups. The alkene protons of an α , β -unsaturated carbonyl compound are affected by the electron-withdrawing carbonyl group in different ways; the α -proton is shielded (lower ppm) and the β -proton is deshielded (higher ppm). Hence, the protons on C-3 and C-4 can be assigned as 6.56 ppm and 7.51 ppm, respectively. The oxymethyl group attached to C-4 of the aromatic ring has a similar effect. The protons situated *ortho* to the ether group are shielded, while the *meta* protons are deshielded. This allows the remaining protons, at positions C-2' and C-3', to be assigned as 7.50 ppm and 6.89 ppm, respectively.

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